

Strelitzia reginae Bird of paradise

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Phylum: Magnoliophyta

Estimated genome size: 739 million DNA base pairs (0.74 Gigabases)

Organism size: 2 meters in height

Distribution:

Native to South Africa, bird of paradise plants occurs naturally in the Eastern Cape, Western Cape, and KwaZulu-Natal. It grows along riverbanks and in coastal thickets.

Importance:

The crane flower, bird of paradise, or isigude in Nguni, is one of South Africa's most iconic flowering plants. As an evergreen perennial with striking orange and blue flowers it is highly sought after for gardens and the cut flower market and, therefore, widely cultivated for its aesthetic appeal.

PromethION Sequencing Report: Output: 43.63 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 7.69 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Genome length: 597.23 million bases (0.60 Gigabases)

BUSCO completeness score (single and duplicated genes): 99.3%

[Single: 57.3%, Duplicated: 42.0%]

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